

YASHIL

**IQTISODIYOT
va
TARAQQIYOT**

*Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik,
ilmiy, ommabop jurnal*

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RIVOJLANTIRISHDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI,
IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA AUDITNING ROLI HAMDA
ISTIQBOLDAGI VAZIFALAR" MAVZUSIDAGI
XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA**

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THE STATUS OF ACCOUNTING TODAY

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Abstract: This article examines the role of accounting in the activities of an enterprise (company), in making managerial decisions, and in interacting with other departments and services. It is proposed to pay attention to the changes taking place in the world, which entail changes in accounting itself, as well as in the professions of an accountant and auditor. The TOP 10 skills necessary for a modern accountant are presented.

Key words: accounting, accounting skills, changes, management decisions, financial sector, taxes.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola korxon (kompaniya) faoliyatida, boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilishda, boshqa bo'limlar va xizmatlar bilan o'zaro aloqada buxgalteriya hisobining rolini o'rganadi. Dunyoda ro'y berayotgan o'zgarishlarga e'tibor qaratish taklif etiladi, bu esa buxgalteriya hisobining o'zida, shuningdek, buxgalter va auditorlik kasblarida o'zgarishlarga olib keladi. Zamonaviy buxgalter uchun zarur bo'lgan TOP 10 ta ko'nikmalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: buxgalteriya hisobi, hisob ko'nikmalari, o'zgarishlar, boshqaruv qarorlari, moliya sektori, soliqlar.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль бухгалтерского учета в деятельности предприятия (компании), в принятии управленческих решений, во взаимодействии с другими подразделениями и службами. Предлагается обратить внимание на изменения, происходящие в мире, влекущие за собой изменения в самом бухучете, а также в профессиях бухгалтера, аудитора. Представлен ТОП 10 навыков, необходимых современному бухгалтеру.

Ключевые слова: бухгалтерский учет, навыки бухгалтера, изменения, управленческие решения, финансовый сектор, налоги.

Things are changing fast in the modern world. When quantity accumulates, qualitative changes are followed by qualitative ones. It is very important not only that we must respond to this, but also how to respond. We can structure some changes, some not [1]. These changes affect practically all areas of activity, including accounting.

Accounting plays a major role in the company's management system. With the development of the market economy, enterprises and organizations face the need to justify each of their steps. To do this, the company's management must have objective and complete information about the costs of acquiring resources, the planned and actual cost of products, the expected and received profits, and other factors affecting the business processes and results of the company's activities. Accounting is designed to collect and process such information at the enterprise.

In the Regulations on Accounting and Financial Reporting of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Order of the President of Uzbekistan dated 04-13-2016 No. 404) [2], the main tasks facing accounting at the current stage of the development of economic relations are formulated. These tasks include: formation of complete and reliable information about the organization's activities and its financial position, necessary for internal users of accounting statements – managers, founders and owners of the organization's property, as well as external users – investors, creditors, etc.; providing information necessary for internal and external users of accounting statements to monitor compliance with the legislation of the Russian Federation when conducting business

operations by the organization and their expediency, the availability and movement of property and obligations, the use of material, labor and financial resources in accordance with approved norms, standards and estimates; prevention of negative results of the organization's business activities and identification of on-farm reserves to ensure its financial stability. To effectively perform the tasks set, they use the functions performed by accounting in the enterprise management system: information and control; the information function is one of the main accounting functions. And this is understandable, since accounting is a place where information flows intersect at an enterprise. It is here that all information about business activities from different divisions and services of the enterprise is collected, adds up the overall picture of a division of the enterprise. All further activities of the enterprise depend on how timely, complete and accurate information about resources, income and obligations is. Without such information, it is impossible to solve current problems, and even more so to make plans for the future; the control function is no less important in accounting. Since accounting reflects all economic transactions without exception in a single monetary estimate, this allows us to take into account and control the use of an enterprise's economic assets and manage them rationally. It is these accounting properties that make it possible to reflect all changes (both positive and negative). The control function allows you to prevent and suppress postings, abuse, comply with the economy regime, rationally use material and labor resources, and preserve property. Thus, the accounting control function helps to increase the profitability of enterprises. Speaking the language of indicators and accurate data, accounting is able to most accurately tell about the property and economic situation of an enterprise. It allows you to make weighted and effective decisions based on them; effective management decisions; analyze the activities of the organization for any reporting period; develop plans for its further development; monitor ongoing work. Accounting data make it possible to understand whether the company's activities bring profit, whether the current policy in the field of production and sales is effective, and whether expansion of activities is required.

Accounting helps to make a decision in any non-standard situation, determine the future policy of the company and attract potential investors.

Knowledge of accounting is required to work in the financial sector in the West. Accounting and reporting provide the basis for making managerial decisions. You need to be able to read the reports from different angles. It is important for the director of an enterprise to work in the internal audit and control service. He has to understand this thoroughly. Therefore, we must constantly learn and develop. There is a lot of talk now that the profession of accountant and auditor may die out. In my opinion, this is not a completely correct statement. Of course, these professions will undergo changes, as the electronic budget system is already being implemented, accounting departments are being centralized, it is assumed that the balance sheet will not be submitted for verification, but the general ledger will be submitted, and the "primary" will be uploaded. An increasing number of projects are related not just to financial audits, but to efficiency audits, process audits, and strategic audits. Almost everyone is currently working on information products: 1C, SAP, ASL.uz, etc. Therefore, information audit becomes important. In this regard, the requirements for an accountant, auditor, and economist in terms of knowledge of the subject area, including information products, will increase. The new specialist will need to have IT knowledge. Perhaps there will be a new IT implementation specialist with knowledge of accounting and control. The integration of accounting specialists' skills with those of specialists in other related fields will only increase. In the digital age, the sustainable development of the economy depends on the ability of specialists to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in the place and at the time when it is most convenient for them [2]. A customer-oriented approach will become increasingly important. Those who can build a control system for the supplier to make important decisions will be successful [1]. According to a survey of respondents, directors and HR specialists conducted by companies such as Norma.uz, Lex.uz, and HR Director, the TOP 10 skills with which an accountant "will be in great demand" were developed [3-4-5]: The ability to reduce taxes (87% of employers are looking for such a specialist). Experience or "burning eyes", willingness to work and increased qualification. Combining the duties of the chief accountant and the finance director (the ability to make estimates and budget is important). Management accounting. Knowledge of personnel matters. Ability to work and communicate in a team. Responsibility. The ability to talk simply about complex things. Communication. Organizational skills. As a result of the same survey, it was highlighted that employers who are looking for an accounting specialist do not particularly need, for example, knowledge of IFRS/GAAP, legal knowledge, or a master's degree. Thus, accounting is undergoing changes, but it still remains the language of business, serving as a universal translator. It allows all reporting users to speak the same language and understand each other. It translates the completed business operations and the results of the company's activities into a single, universal language of numbers and indicators that are understandable to all interested parties.

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